
Exploring BIM Capabilities for Life Cycle Assessment in Structural Projects: Towards Sustainable Material Choices

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The construction sector significantly contributes to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, resource consumption, and waste production, with structural materials accounting for up to 40% of embedded carbon emissions. Addressing this challenge requires early-stage selection of sustainable materials, supported by accurate environmental data. This study investigates the integration of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and Finite Element Analysis (FEA) with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tools to enhance sustainable structural design. Using a case study of a traditional Valencian barraca modelled in Autodesk Revit, three design scenarios were evaluated: traditional materials (adobe and wood), concrete with steel, and concrete with Cross-Laminated Timber (CLT). The structural design relied on BIM for modelling and material quantification, combined with FEA tools (Autodesk Robot and Dlubal RFEM) for structural analysis. Three LCA tools—Tally, Tekla Structural Designer, and One Click LCA—were tested for interoperability and their ability to assess the environmental impacts of structural materials. Results indicate that Scenario 1 had the lowest Global Warming Potential (GWP) due to natural materials, while Scenario 2 exhibited the highest emissions from steel and concrete. Scenario 3 demonstrated the potential of timber to partially offset emissions through biogenic carbon sequestration. This research proposes a workflow integrating BIM, FEA, and LCA processes to incorporate sustainability metrics into structural design, enabling informed decision-making and compliance with environmental regulations. Key recommendations include advancing EPD standardisation, developing structural-specific benchmarks, and enabling real-time data integration between BIM and LCA tools. These findings highlight the potential of digital methodologies to decarbonise the construction sector.

Keywords – BIM integration, FEA, Life Cycle Assessment, sustainable materials, structural design, carbon footprint

I INTRODUCTION

a) Climate Change and the Role of Structures in the Construction Industry

Natural disasters are becoming more intense and frequent, all life on the planet is suffering by the adverse human activity (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). The construction sector is a major contributor to global climate change due to its high energy consumption, intensive use of raw materials, and extensive greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which are the primary driver of global warming (Win, 2021). Furthermore, the accommodation emergency leads to a rise in the number of houses constructed in the coming years (Valencia *et al.*, 2021). Given that structures are a significant part of the building industry which accounts for approximately 35-40% of the embedded carbon footprint (Bartolomé, 2024),

the material characteristics are pivotal to reach sustainability targets like the landmark Paris Agreement goal of limiting the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels, which requires at least a 43% reduction of the GHG emissions by 2030 (Arce Romero, 2024).

b) Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Carbon Footprint

LCA is a standardized methodology that evaluates the environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product's lifecycle, from raw material extraction to disposal. Specifically, the extraction, manufacturing, transport, or use of materials in construction processes embodies CHG emissions (British Standards Institution, 2021). Also, buildings or infrastructure release additional GHG emissions during the operational phase due to the energy use and

resources consumed (National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI), 2011). Accordingly, researchers quantify GHG emissions, both embodied and operative using the metric of equivalent carbon dioxide (CO₂e), which is quantitative representation of the GHG sent out for each process, commonly referred to as the carbon footprint. Therefore, this enables structural design teams to make informed, data-driven decisions that prioritize material sustainability.

c) *Building Information Modelling (BIM) and Sustainability*

Experts increasingly recognize BIM as a rapidly evolving collaborative tool for enhancing design in construction projects (Morsi *et al.*, 2022). By enabling the integration of the 3D model and data during the initial stages (Bynum *et al.*, 2012), BIM supports simulation of building performance and selection of sustainable materials and optimizes resource use. However, Eastman states that “*Models that contain 3D data only and no object attributes can only be used for graphic visualizations and have no intelligence at the object level*” (Eastman *et al.*, 2008). As a result, raising maturity to, at least, BIM Stage 2, is essential to maximize its benefits for sustainability purposes in structural design (Succar, 2009).

d) *BIM and LCA for structural design*

This study sets out to investigate the integration of BIM and LCA for structural design. The purpose of this study is to analyse how BIM tools can facilitate the extraction of environmental data, such as carbon footprint, water consumption, and energy use, to support sustainable material selection during the design phase.

It begins with a review of the benefits associated with combining LCA methodologies with BIM workflows. Followed by the examination of current tools for implementing LCA in BIM environments. Finally, the author proposes a systematic workflow for embedding LCA into structural design using BIM.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

a) *Sustainability in Construction*

BS-EN 15643:2021 defines sustainability in construction as the ability to assess the environmental, social, and economic performance of buildings using quantitative indicators. This standard emphasizes that sustainability must meet present needs without compromising those of future generations (British Standards Institution, 2021). To better understand one key metric of sustainability, the notation kgCO₂e (kilograms of CO₂ equivalent) is introduced. Each greenhouse gas has a different Global Warming Potential (GWP), meaning some

gases contribute to global warming much more significantly than CO₂. To compare these gases on a common scale, their impacts are converted to an equivalent amount of CO₂ (Adams and Goggins, 2024).

A critical aspect of sustainability in construction is embodied energy, defined as the energy consumed during the extraction, manufacture, and transportation of materials. Historically, the focus has been on improving operational energy efficiency but reports increasingly recognise the energy impact of the construction phase as a significant contributor to a building's overall sustainability profile. This dual challenge of operational and embodied energy is evident in global energy consumption. United Nations Environment Programme (2024) report highlights that construction accounts for approximately 37% of global energy consumption, including both operational energy during a building's life and the energy embedded in construction materials. Even, the same UN report states that materials like cement and steel, essential for most structures, are not only carbon-intensive but also energy-intensive, reinforcing the need for sustainable material selection.

Building emissions, a major concern in sustainable construction, are classified into operational carbon and embedded carbon. According to the 2023 Global Status Report for Buildings and Construction, operational CO₂ emissions reached a record high of 9.8 gigatonnes in 2022, surpassing the pre-pandemic peak of 2019. Alarmingly, this figure is 40% above the baseline needed to align with 2030 reduction targets set by the Paris Agreement (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). To combat these trends, global and regional initiatives have emerged. For instance, the EU's *Fit for 55* aims to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 55% by 2030, while the European Green Deal targets climate neutrality by 2050. A key part of these efforts involves decarbonizing the building sector by addressing both operational and embedded carbon. Despite these goals, national initiatives remain limited, though programs like the American SE 2050 Commitment allow structural engineers and companies to pledge to reduce the carbon footprint of their projects (*SE 2050 Challenge - Carbon Leadership Forum*, no date). The author has not found a direct equivalent in Europe.

The construction industry's demand for natural resources further complicates sustainability. It is responsible for extracting up to 50% of global raw materials, generating 35% of solid waste, and using 20% of water. Additionally, the sector occupies 10% of urban land and produces around 30% of total waste from human activities (Woodea, 2024). These statistics highlight the industry's considerable environmental footprint.

Focusing specifically on structures, the superstructure of a conventional building accounts for 35–40% of the total embedded carbon footprint. Consequently, reducing emissions in this domain is critical for addressing the broader environmental impact of the AECO (Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations) industry. Given the longevity of structural elements—often exceeding 50 years—it is essential to prioritize materials that, despite high initial energy costs, offer durability and recyclability, thereby reducing long-term environmental impact (BIMrras, 2022; Bartolomé, 2024; Woodea, 2024). To systematically address these challenges, National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI), vol. (2011, vol. EN 15978), the European standard for assessing the environmental performance of buildings, divides a building's lifecycle into four primary stages with detailed modules for environmental impact assessment:

- Product Stage (Modules A1–A3): Covers material extraction and manufacturing.
- Construction Process Stage (Modules A4–A5): Includes transportation and construction activities.
- Use Stage (Modules B1–B7): Considers operational impacts such as maintenance and energy use.
- End-of-Life Stage (Modules C1–C4): Focuses on demolition and waste processing.
- Beyond Building Life Cycle (Module D): Explores circular economy benefits, such as material reuse or recycling.

By structuring assessments through these stages, EN 15978 offers a comprehensive framework for identifying specific areas where environmental impacts can be mitigated (RIB Software GmbH, 2024). As buildings become more energy-efficient and renewable energy replaces fossil fuels, operational emissions will decline in significance. This shift underscores the importance of focusing on the design phase to select structural materials with lower embedded carbon. Early-stage decisions can significantly reduce a building's lifecycle carbon footprint, emphasizing the need for initiative-taking, sustainable material selection strategies (Soust-Verdaguer, 2023).

Life cycle assessment (LCA) practices and tools are essential for addressing the challenges associated with decarbonizing building structures. By quantifying environmental impacts during the early design phases, LCA enables stakeholders to make informed decisions that can significantly reduce emissions in construction projects (Bernardette Soust-Verdaguer *et al.*, 2024). One of the key

components supporting LCA is the use of Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs). These technical documents provide detailed information about the environmental impacts of product manufacturing processes. Functioning as Type II ecolabels, EPDs are grounded in LCA methodology and evaluate critical environmental aspects such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, natural resource usage, water consumption, and waste generation. Importantly, third parties verify EPDs to ensure their accuracy and transparency (Woodea, 2024). The Environmental Product Declarations system has evolved to include 24 official indicators in its latest version, offering a comprehensive framework for assessing product impacts.

Among the indicators, several are particularly significant in evaluating environmental performance (*Environmental Performance Indicators | EPD International*, no date):

- Global Warming Potential (GWP): Measures greenhouse gas emissions across various sources, including fossil, biogenic, and land use changes.
- Acidification Potential (AP): Assesses potential acidifying emissions, which impact soil and water quality.
- Eutrophication Potential (EP): Evaluates nutrient runoff that can lead to aquatic ecosystem imbalances, with indicators for freshwater, marine, and terrestrial environments.
- Photochemical Ozone Creation Potential (POCP): Measures the potential for ground-level ozone formation, affecting air quality and human health.
- Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP): Focuses on emissions contributing to the degradation of the ozone layer.
- Abiotic Depletion Potential (ADP): Separates into indicators for the depletion of mineral/metal and fossil resources.
- Water Deprivation Potential (WDP): Accounts for the potential impact of water consumption on water scarcity, measured via the AWARE method.

b) *BIM Capabilities in Environmental Data Extraction*

Baldwin (2019) defines BIM as a method of using digital models to support the design, construction, and operation of built facilities. However, it is an activity (building information modelling) rather than just an object (building information model). It emphasizes the process, and the human activity involved in

creating and managing building data (Eastman *et al.*, 2008). Previous researchers have indicated that the information generated through the BIM model can be shared with project partners via a Common Data Environment (CDE), fostering collaboration and allowing the structural engineer to access the workflows and data of all team members (McLoughlin and Mcauley, 2022). Furthermore, Structural Analysis is explicitly part of the listed in Penn State's 21 BIM Uses, focusing on analysing and verifying the structural integrity of the design using BIM models. On the other hand, Sustainability Assessment is not explicitly labelled as a standalone category, but it can be considered as part of Energy Analysis, Lighting Analysis, or integrated into Environmental Performance Analysis. These collectively address the assessment of sustainability criteria using BIM, such as energy efficiency, carbon footprint, and lifecycle impacts. (Baldwin, 2019).

To fully leverage BIM's potential, model's dimensions must be extended beyond 3D, including 4D, which represents the analysis of the duration and planning of the project, 5D corresponding to the analysis of costs, measurements and budgets, 6D, referring to the sustainability assessment, and 7D, which integrates management and maintenance throughout the life cycle (Diego Cabrero, 2019). Achieving this level of integration requires a specific degree of BIM maturity. According to the BIM framework proposed by Succar (2009), maturity is composed of three components: technology, process and policies, and is divided into three stages, in the case that concerns us BIM Stage 2: model-based collaboration, is the minimum level necessary to effectively implement collaborative workflows in structural and sustainability-focused projects.

c) Integration of LCA Tools

Aparecido Lopes Silva *et al.* (2017) highlight the significance of parametric LCA BIM tools focusing on operational and embodied energy perspectives, indicating a practical approach to enhancing sustainability through BIM-LCA integration. In the same way, Bernardette Soust-Verdaguer *et al.* (2024) emphasizes the importance of using BIM to reduce embodied energy in construction and improve energy efficiency in buildings, displaying the potential benefits of integrating BIM with LCA tools.

During the design phase, the size of structural elements impacts not only their direct carbon footprint but also the entire building. Larger elements increase building height, façade surface, and foundation size, all contributing to a higher carbon footprint. For instance, a 1 cm increase in slab depth adds 25 kg/m² in weight and 2.36 kg CO₂e/m² in emissions (Bartolomé, 2024). To reduce embedded carbon, optimizing element size and weight is crucial.

Structural analysis must include life cycle carbon footprint assessments using LCA and BIM models to evaluate scenarios with varied materials (*Building Information Model Creation Guidelines for Model Use with One Click LCA*, no date).

d) Challenges and Limitations

Among the main challenges, the lack of homogeneous and reliable data stands out. Databases such as Eco Platform and OpenLCA provide access to sustainability information, but they often present problems of consistency and coverage. Consequently, ISO 22057 establishes guidelines for structuring sustainability data in BIM models, improving consistency and accessibility, although the full implementation of these standards still faces technical and regulatory barriers (BIMrras, 2022). Another setback is that the units of measurement of the measurements may not coincide with the functional units of the EPDs (Woodea, 2024). Additionally, to have real and homogeneous results of LCAs and EPDs is essential to establish benchmark values for carbon emissions throughout a building's life cycle (B Soust-Verdaguer *et al.*, 2024; Rey-Alvarez, Soust-Verdaguer and Garcia-Martinez, 2024).

The eLCA tool, developed by the Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs, and Spatial Development in Germany, facilitates the evaluation of the environmental impact of building materials and technical systems throughout a building's entire life cycle. To improve interoperability, BIM2SIM project, involving the Institute for Energy Efficient Buildings and Indoor Climate and the Institute of Energy Efficiency and Sustainable Building at RWTH Aachen University, Germany along with ROM Technik GmbH developed an interface to connect IFC files with the eLCA tool. This integration allows for the automated transfer of key data from IFC files, including material names, quantities, areas, and volumes, while also enabling the addition of supplementary information such as cost group classifications (Jansen *et al.*, 2021).

e) Practical Applications and Case Studies

Various case studies highlight practical applications of BIM for sustainability. Morsi *et al.* (2022) effectively demonstrate how BIM tools can quantify life LCA metrics for residential buildings by comparing structural systems to evaluate embodied carbon and environmental impacts. Similarly, Lobos *et al.* (2024) emphasize the integration of BIM in wood construction, highlighting its potential for reducing carbon footprints and optimizing workflows.

The World Green Building Council (2023) report provides insights into policy-driven applications of whole-life carbon assessments, while Valencia *et al.*

(2021) outlines strategies for decarbonization in the construction sector in Chile. Furthermore, projects like BIM2SIM, mentioned in point four, integrate BIM with tools like eLCA for automated LCA data extraction, streamlining sustainable material selection (Jansen *et al.*, 2021). These examples illustrate how BIM tools and methodologies can facilitate sustainability in construction through real-world applications. In like manner Woodea (2024), a company specializing in industrialized construction, published a corporate report that compares three cases of low-impact industrialized construction, focusing on water, waste, and carbon.

III PRIMARY RESEARCH

a) Overview

The chosen primary research method on which to carry out analyses and draw conclusions later is a case study on which the different workflows and tools will be tested through the integration of BIM, FEA and LCA processes. This will provide quantitative data for further analysis, as well as qualitative data by means of actual experience from the user's point of view.

The BIM model chosen for the case study is an architectural model in Autodesk Revit 2023.1 format previously modelled by the author (Selfa, 2023), consisting of a traditional farmer's house known as a "barraca", located in Valencia (Spain). It is a detached single-family house with two floors: the ground floor and the first floor as an attic under a gabled roof. The total usable area is 88.44 m², approximately 104.00 m² built.

b) Structural System and Scenarios

The structural model is created with the required Level of Information Need (LoIN), corresponding to RIAI Stage 3: Developed Design (RIAI, 2022), using the same Autodesk tool. The structural system is composed of eight trusses supported on lateral load-bearing walls whose foundations will be continuous footings. The ground level is a floor resting on the ground and partially on its perimeter on the foundations of the load-bearing side walls, while that the first floor will be a light framework simply supported on the lower chords of the triangular trusses that constitute eight parallel frames. Using the tool that Revit provides for this purpose, the structural model has three material design options that will be the scenarios that will be used later to compare its carbon footprints using LCA. One of these scenarios will be with the one that uses traditional materials, the

second will be with concrete and steel, the third will be with wood.

The structural system and general volumetry are maintained in all scenarios, varying the structural materials as indicated in Table 1. For scenario 1, the traditional materials and dimensions of the structural elements are respected. While in scenarios 2 and 3 the materials of the elements are simply changed, but the dimensions of scenario 1 are maintained. For example, in the case of steel elements, rolled profiles of the dimensions closest to those of scenario 1 are chosen. A basic structural analysis is carried out with the finite element tool in order to check the structural feasibility of the scenarios as well as the integration of the FEA tools in the workflow, but it is not intended to optimize the quantities of structural materials since it is a small project the impact on the LCA would be minimal, but mainly because design is not the object of this study, which is focused on the interoperability of the different methodologies.

Table 1

Structural Materials for Each Scenario

	Foundations	Floor	Walls	Beams
Scenario 1	Adobe bricks and stone	Rammed earth	Adobe bricks	Wood
Scenario 2	Concrete	Concrete	Concrete	Steel
Scenario 3	Concrete	Wood (CLT)	Wood (CLT)	Wood

The analysis of these scenarios is designed to assess the environmental impacts associated with material selection, following the methodology detailed in subsequent sections.

c) Tools and Workflow

For the structural analysis, the author has based his knowledge and availability of use of licenses to choose the FEA tools. This means that Autodesk Robot 2023 and Dlubal RFEM 6.07 have been used, both with a direct link to Revit via plugins. The Revit plugin has also been used to export to Tekla Structural Designer, although the main purpose was not the structural analysis but to obtain a carbon report using the tool that Trimble incorporates natively for the A1-A3 modules of the life cycle, that is Cradle to Gate. That is only the carbon embodied in the materials of the structure by the production, and not the carbon emitted in transport, construction or operation. It is important to note that, although Tekla SD offers a link with One Click LCA for the analysis of the complete life cycle, it is not used in this study as it is not included in the educational license obtained.

The process map in Figure 1 illustrates an integrated workflow combining BIM, FEA, and LCA. Starting with structural modelling in Revit, it transitions through structural analysis (Robot, RFEM) and life

cycle assessment (Tally, One Click LCA, Tekla Structural Designer). Iterative feedback optimizes structural integrity and environmental performance, informing sustainable design.

Figure 1

BIM/FEA/LCA Structural Project Workflow and Tools

d) Life Cycle Assessment Methodology

The author has relied on international standards to guide the structured and coherent implementation of the LCA. The definition of objectives and scope of the LCA is established in the international standard I.S. EN ISO 14040, additionally the I.S. EN ISO 14044, develops how to define them. In this case study they are:

- Objective:
 - Support decisions in the choice of materials in structural design.
- Scope:
 - Functional unit: structure for approximately 104.00 m² built (88.44 m² usable area) for a calculation period of 60 years. Divided between ground floor and attic. All three scenarios use the same structural system with different materials.
 - System Frontiers: Cradle to Grave analysis, covering all stages, according to the I.S. EN 15978 standard. Using the One Click LCA Cloud tool by reading the BIM model.

- Additionally, a Cradle to Gate analysis is performed with the Tally and One Click LCA tools for Revit and Tekla Structural Designer.

○ The data for this study will be obtained from EPDs available in databases such as One Click LCA. The concept and relevance of EPDs were previously explained in the Literature Review under section 'a) Sustainability in Construction'.

○ Transport and construction data (A4-A5) are accepted for averages based on typical scenarios in construction projects provided by the tools, both for material transport distances and for electricity, energy and water consumption on site.

- No consumption is estimated for the repair, replacement or rehabilitation modules (B3-B5) since the duration of any structural element is expected to be less than 60 years (Woodea, 2024).
- Although it is known that energy changes affect emissions over time due to the decarbonization of the electricity mix (García, 2004), for the operational energy use module (B6) of this study, the emission factor of the current grid multiplied by the energy consumption of the life cycle of the building based on average consumptions published by the Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía has been considered (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico, no date).
- It is estimated for this study that the structure represents 37.5% of the total work (Bartolomé, 2024). This percentage has been applied to water and energy consumption in the operations phase and subsequent phases. The same will be applied to

the ranges of the benchmarks so that the comparisons are consistent.

- Of the sustainability indicators in buildings and infrastructure works described in the ISO 21931 standard, only GWP will be analysed, although the relevance of the rest of the environmental impacts is recognised.
- Specific considerations:
 - The author has located and learned about the tools used for the study of LCA, as explained in the literature review section, with special focus on those that allow integration with BIM models, directly, through plugin, with an exchange file, or with a link through a cloud application through the internet. Finally, three have been chosen, following criteria of availability of academic licenses that allow their evaluation, as well as functionalities offered and the author's knowledge or learning possibilities within the time of this study. Table 2 summarizes these tools.

Table 2

LCA Tools used in the Case Study

	Type	Comments
One Click LCA	Revit plugin and Cloud	Green Buildings 2020/2022 tool for Cradle to Grave
One Click LCA	Cloud	Only modules A1-A3. Cradle to Gate (Production)
Tally	Revit plugin	Whole life cycle, Cradle to Grave
Tekla Design	Structural Native tool	Only modules A1-A3. Cradle to Gate (Production)

- BIM modelling and limitations:
 - BIM models will be developed with a LoIN suitable for Developed Design (IS EN ISO 19650-1, 2018; IS EN ISO 19650-2, 2021), but which may limit accuracy in certain detailed calculations in later phases. That is why the LCA needs to be repeated as the level of development and information of the model increases (Soust-Verdaguer, 2023).
 - It is also important to note the limitations regarding the BIM modelling tool, its version and the compatibility of the LCA plugin, as

this will affect us. This case study is modelled in Revit 2023.1 since Tally is not compatible with the 2025 version as One Click LCA is.

- Regarding the openBIM options, as concluded after the literature review, the options are few and limiting in terms of process automation and use of EPD databases, so they have been discarded in this case study.
- Expected results:
 - Tally is based on EPDs from the US market. Therefore, although it is possible to refine aspects such as the distances of transport of the materials, at the end of the process the results are conditioned by the data used.
 - Estimated distances. Due to the educational characteristics of the project and its fictitious location, the author considers valid the distances proposed by the different tools that, in the case of Tally should be adjusted in a real project, but in the case of One

Click LCA they are quite realistic as they are based on the country of origin of the EPD of each product.

○ The Benchmark charts offered by One Click templates are unrepresentative as they are not intended for structural projects. They are generally of complete

constructions and in some cases without installations (MEP). However, they serve as a basis on which to make estimates as will be described in the results analysis section.

e) Implementation of the Workflow

Depending on the types of tools involved, a different workflow is required, although the goal is always to seek the best interoperability from a BIM point of view for each step, either through direct linking or by intermediate exchange files. The process aims to obtain the necessary data to evaluate the sustainability of the structural materials used in a BIM model using LCA tools in an integrated manner with FEA tools.

Although this case begins with the modelling of the structure in Revit based on the architectural model, it is not an essential requirement since structural modelling can commence independently, simultaneously or prior to the architectural modelling. For the case study developed, the Revit design options tool has been used to recreate the different scenarios described in the previous sections. For the modelling, materials from the Revit library were assigned to the structural elements in scenarios 2 and 3, but since equivalent standard materials were not available, the author created the traditional materials of scenario 1 by entering their density and other physical properties manually.

Next, an analytical model has been created from the physical model, including loads and combinations, for export to structural analysis tools. At this point, as previously explained in this document, a basic structural analysis is carried out with the materials of each scenario by the FEA method, using the Robot Structural Analysis and Dlubal RFEM 6 tools to integrate the tools into the workflow. The analytical model has also been exported from Revit to Tekla Structural Designer to obtain the Cradle to Gate (A1-A3) carbon footprint report.

Subsequently, the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) shown in Table 3 has been carried out, in which the inputs and outputs have been identified. As inputs for each of the scenarios, the measurements of the materials used will be extracted from the BIM model. This

Table 3

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI). Structural materials (m³)

Scenario	Earth	Gravel	Stone	Adobe Bricks	Concrete	Steel	Wood
Scenario 1	9.81	4.54	3.41	26.27	-	-	4.27
Scenario 2	-	-	-	-	47.32	0.27	-
Scenario 3	-	-	-	-	16.61	-	28.67

Note. This table is based on Revit materials scheduling.

Table 4

Global Warming Potential (GWP) in Kg CO₂eq/m². Cradle to Gate (A1-A3)

	Tally	Tekla SD	One Click LCA plugin
Scenario 1 (traditional)	162.6	164.03	36
Scenario 2 (concrete + steel)	259.3	282.37	179

collection of inputs allows LCI outputs to be obtained in the form of greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂e), waste, resource consumption, etc.

To complete the process, using One Click LCA, Tally and Tekla Structural Designer, the quantities of materials from the BIM model were imported and

mapped by their equivalent materials in the EPD databases of the tested tools. We then proceed to enter the rest of the necessary data, such as the proportional part of energy and water used during production, transport, construction and the operations phase. The calculation carried out with all this leads to the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), which consists of quantifying environmental impacts using indicators such as GWP, primary energy consumption, water consumption or waste generation. Finally, the results were integrated into the full LCA framework to assess comparative sustainability across scenarios.

IV FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

a) Findings

Quantitative Results:

Global Warming Potential Comparison. Each scenario was assessed using three LCA tools: Tally, Tekla Structural Designer, and One Click LCA. Table 4 shows the GWP for each scenario involving the embodied carbon of the structural materials emitted for the production phase:

- Scenario 1 showed the lowest GWP due to the natural materials.
- Scenario 2 had significantly higher emissions, due to the carbon intensity of steel and concrete.

- Scenario 3 demonstrated the potential of wood in carbon sequestration, which partially offsets the emissions of concrete.

Table 5 shows the global warming intensity that each material participating in one or more of the scenarios that this study has during the production phase.

Qualitative Insights:

- BIM Modelling Feedback:

- Strengths: The direct extraction of material quantities from the BIM model facilitated accurate

LCA inputs. One Click LCA and Tally effectively linked with Revit for streamlined data exchange (Carroll, 2024).

Table 5*GWP Intensities (A1-A3) in KgCO₂e/Kg.*

Material	Tally	Tekla SD	One Click LCA
Adobe bricks and stone	N/A	0.150	N/A
Rammed earth	N/A	N/A	N/A
Concrete (cast-in-place)	0.150	0.150	0.150-0.180
Structural steel (hot-rolled)	1.580	1.580	~1.5-1.6
Reinforcement bars (loose)	1.960	1.960	~1.960
Timber (CLT)	0.437	0.437	~0.437

Notes. Some traditional materials do not have detailed GWP data in the tools used.

- Challenges: Keeping the physical elements correctly linked to their analytical equivalent is key, since in this way the materials can be updated when changing from one scenario to another. In contrast, this can be particularly difficult in larger projects, with many more elements and in which not only a change of material, but also of the structural system is made (Moret, 2021).
- LCA Tools Feedback:
 - Autodesk Insight: The tool was tested but faced several challenges. While it uses the EC3 database, like Tally, the creation of an Energy Analytical Model (EAM) proved problematic. Issues such as unsupported elements, design configurations, and missing components limited its applicability. For example, when applied to a full architectural model, the tool worked; however, when focusing on open structural spaces, it failed to generate valid EAMs, highlighting its limitations for structural analysis (*Autodesk Insight | Building Performance Analysis Software*, no date).
 - One Click LCA: Provided the most comprehensive integration with BIM and localised EPD databases, to perform LCA. EPDs, verified by third parties, are directly integrated into the software to evaluate environmental impacts of materials and processes, such as carbon footprint, energy, and water consumption, adjusting calculations to local standards (EN 15804) and accounting for transportation and production (*Short Guide to BIM Modelling for LCA*

automation – One Click LCA Help Centre, no date).

- Tally: Effective for real-time analysis but limited by its use of databases based on EPDs from the U.S. market to calculate environmental impacts. Tally does not allow importing external EPDs, parameters such as transport distances and material equivalences must be manually adjusted to reflect local conditions. Additionally, its design options comparison feature was useful to assess the embodied carbon footprint (*Tally | About | Overview*, no date).

- Tekla Structural Designer: Relied on predefined Embodied Carbon Factors (ECFs) or manual inputs, with limited integration of external databases (García, 2004). Additionally, errors in the building's total area calculations required manual correction, highlighting the need for improved automation and accuracy in outputs.

b) Analysis

The analysis aims to address the research question: “How can BIM be leveraged to support LCA for sustainable material selection in structural projects?” by examining interoperability and data flow within the proposed workflow. The study highlighted that BIM integration with LCA tools is feasible but dependent on:

Integration and Workflow Observations

BIM Maturity (as introduced in Primary Research and referenced in Literature Review) BIM Stage 2 or higher is essential to harness the full potential of sustainability assessments (McAuley, Hore and West, 2019).

Limitations in interoperability were noted, particularly when integrating multiple plugins and exporting analytical models as mentioned in the Literature Review section. Obstacles have been encountered that have prevented or hindered the use of several tools, not only among those of different developers, but also with plugins to be used within Revit. For example, Beacon | Thornton Tomasetti (no date) plugin is only available for Revit 2018-2022 or Tally plugin is not compatible with Revit 2025.

In relation to interoperable formats, structural modelling uses the same as the rest of the AECO industry, mostly IFC. There is even the BIM2SIM initiative, mentioned in the Literature Review, which provides an interface between IFC and the German eLCA Tool (Jansen *et al.*, 2021). In turn, the Autodesk Green Building Studio tool has gbXML file as the format accepted in its specifications (*Green Building Studio*, no date). Another option that is gaining more and more strength in BIM processes to overcome interoperability problems is Speckle, a tool that hosts the models in the cloud and delivers them converted to the format of each desktop tool, allowing synchronization.

The challenges with generating analytical elements in Revit 2023, discussed in Primary Research, highlight the complexity of maintaining model consistency across scenarios (Coya Piñero, 2022). It is necessary to ensure the correct link between each physical structural element and its corresponding analytical element before it is exported for the structural analysis software. It is important to remember that despite having multiple design options with different materials in Revit, they all share a single analytical model that is only capable of storing one material, so each design option change must be accompanied by an update to the analytical model, either using the Dynamo tool or manually.

Critical Analysis of Benchmarks

The lack of standardised benchmarks for structural projects hindered comparative analyses (Soust-Verdaguer, 2023). However, it is common to find benchmarks for multiple building types, even for buildings without their MEP, located in specific geographic areas. To address this issue, the author designed an Excel tool to isolate structural contributions by adapting building-level benchmarks. The structural contribution is determined by applying a customizable reduction percentage to the range values of kg CO₂e/m² that determine the categories of the GWP sustainability indicator. It enables users to input general building benchmarks and provides adjusted ranges tailored to structural components. Figures 2, 3 and 4 show the benchmarks calculated with the tool based on 37.5% (Bartolomé, 2024) of the ranges of Spain all building types - 2023 Q3 according to the GWP values of the Tekla Structural Designer reports for each scenario.

Figure 2

Scenario 1 Cradle to grave (A1-A4, B4-B5, C1-C4)

Category	Range Start	Range End	kg CO ₂ e/m ²
A	0	188	← 164.03
B	188	225	
C	225	263	
D	263	300	
E	300	338	
F	338	375	
G	375	>375	

Spain all building types - 2023 Q3 excl. STR 37.5%

Figure 3

Scenario 2 Cradle to grave (A1-A4, B4-B5, C1-C4)

Category	Range Start	Range End	kg CO ₂ e/m ²
A	0	188	← 282.37
B	188	225	
C	225	263	
D	263	300	
E	300	338	
F	338	375	
G	375	>375	

Spain all building types - 2023 Q3 excl. STR 37.5%

Figure 4

Scenario 3 Cradle to grave (A1-A4, B4-B5, C1-C4)

Category	Range Start	Range End	kg CO ₂ e/m ²
A	0	188	← 300.88
B	188	225	
C	225	263	
D	263	300	
E	300	338	
F	338	375	
G	375	>375	

Spain all building types - 2023 Q3 excl. STR 37.5%

This bespoke methodology, not covered in earlier sections, addresses the lack of structural-specific benchmarks.

Discussion on Sustainability Metrics:

For the modules of the construction phase, product sub-phase (A1-A3) their impact is established using the information of the environmental indicator required through their EPDs. However, for the calculation of the impact of transport (A4), the National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI) (2011) establishes local, regional, national and international scopes to make estimates of the transport of materials from the factory to the site. BIMrras (2022) 106-episode states that scopes generate controversy regarding the limits of these areas and that, with current means, transportation could be calculated accurately using geographical information. For example, we know that the maximum distance for transport wood that it is worth it in module A4 is < 4,500 Km (Woodea, 2024).

Finally, by means of a budgeting tool, work items could be assigned and thus obtain the water and energy consumption of the machinery used in the construction, installation sub-phase (A5).

Biogenic carbon, while not extensively discussed in the Literature Review, is a significant factor for timber materials as explained in international standards such as ISO 21930 and EN 15804 + A2 (Woodea, 2024). It accounts for temporary carbon sequestration during growth. Tools like Tally and One Click LCA incorporate biogenic carbon, but their approaches differ. Whereas Tally allows users to include or exclude biogenic carbon in the report based on project requirements One Click LCA automatically accounts for it if specified in the EPDs of materials highlighting the variability in methodologies and its impact on assessments.

There is an inconsistency between the data offered by the sustainability databases tested, such as ECO Invent, Open LCA, Open DAP and cost banks such as those of Centro Online or Cype. In fact, they merely publish data collected by third parties and do not homogenize the samples or process the data. This means that the information provided by them is not always relevant to sustainability (BIMrras, 2022). The inconsistency in units used across different EPDs or

EPD databases present significant challenges for conducting accurate and comparable LCAs. EPDs, which provide standardized data on the environmental impacts of construction materials, often differ in reporting formats. Mixing data from sources using imperial and metric units adds further complexity, as unit standardization requires additional calculations or conversions, increasing the risk of errors. Moreover, discrepancies in temporal or geographical scopes between EPDs can create inconsistencies when comparing materials, potentially introducing biases in decision-making. These challenges highlight the need for improved standardization in EPD reporting to enable more reliable and efficient environmental assessments.

V CONCLUSIONS

The findings from the case study presented in this paper demonstrate that BIM can enhance decision-making processes by its ability to streamline data extraction. Qualitative feedback also identified challenges, such as discrepancies in interoperability and data consistency among LCA tools.

Adopting workflows that integrate sustainability assessments early in the design phase enables compliance with environmental regulations. The benchmarking tool proposed in this study serves as an adaptive method for generating structural-specific benchmarks, addressing the lack of standardised data.

Further studies should explore real-time data integration between BIM and EPD databases by LCA tools. Advancing EPD standardisation remains essential to reduce inconsistencies. Additionally, research into the use of traditional materials like timber in scalable, sustainable housing solutions for global emergencies or natural disasters is recommended.

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